

Aging in India: A Social Concern

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Abstract— Ageing is a universal phenomenon. It is the upshot of demographic transition with a decline in both birth and mortality rates, improved nutrition and a consequent increase in life expectancy. In most of the Indian families, elderly people are not getting proper emotional and physical support. The plight of the widowed women is much worse. This paper intends to discuss the problem a country might face owing to the reverse pyramidal structure and how aging itself become a trauma for the aged people and the society at large.

Keywords: Aging, Gerontology, Health, Social Detachment

I. INTRODUCTION

Ageing is a universal phenomenon. Old age is a natural part of the life-cycle. It is a process of regular changes that occurs in mature and genetically representative organism living under representative environmental conditions as they advance in chronological age. These changes can be anatomical, physiological, psychological and even social and economic. Biological Aging refers to anatomical and physiological changes that occur with change. Biologists are of the opinion that aging begins when growth and development stops. Psychological aging consists of a general decline in the mental abilities that accompany old age. Generally, physical aging precedes mental aging though this is not always the case. The sociological aspect of individual aging is concerned with changes in the circumstances or situations of individual as a member of the family, community and society

Wear and Tear Theories of biological aging propose that aging in humans and other animals is simply the result of universal deteriorative process, that operate in any organized system. The theory asserts that the human body is like a machine and after extensive use individual parts start to wear out. From Societal Perspective, The Disengagement Theory views aging as a process through which society and the individual gradually withdraw or disengage from each other. There is transfer of power from the old to the young making it possible for society to continue to function.

The medical process of aging study is called gerontology and the study of diseases that effects the elderly is called geriatrics. The united nation World Assembly on aging, held at Vienna in 1982, formulated a package of recommendations which gives high priority to research related to development and humanitarian aspects of aging. As the phenomenon of population ageing is becoming a major concern for the policy makers all over the world, for both developed and developing countries during last two decades.

II. AGING: THE INDIAN SCENARIO

At present, India has the second largest population in the world and large increase in the human life expectancy over the years has resulted not only in a very substantial increase in the number of older person but a major shift in the age group of 80 and above. the demographic profile depicts that in the year 2000-2050 the overall population of India will grow by 55% where as population of in their 60 years and above will increase by 326% and those in the age group of 80 by 700% according to department of economic and social affairs, (population division U.N, New York)

Population ageing is the most significant result of the process known as demographic transition. Reduction of fertility leads to a decline in the proportion of the young in the population. Reduction in mortality means a longer life span for individuals. Population ageing involves a shift from high mortality/ high fertility to low mortality/ low fertility and consequently an increased proportion of older people in the total population. India is undergoing such a demographic transition The sequence of high birth rate followed by high death rate until 1951 kept the level of elderly population at a low level. But since 1961 the sharp decline of death rate accompanied by increasing expectancy of life at the age 60 has set in motion the process of aging in India. The relatively faster increase in the elderly population will result in the increase in higher dependency ratio of the population in the non-productive age group. Population of a country is always regarded as an asset unless and until it crosses a

certain limit. As the country is aging, this will affect the economy, because the economic needs of the society will be different in an aging society. More concentration of people in the age group below 18 and above 60 is always been regarded as burden on the younger group and the state because of the need for all aspects of care for the oldest namely socio-economic, financial, health and shelter. Further, the strength of any economy is its productive human resources in younger age brackets. Thus, every ageing nation suffers from over dependency and lesser participation of younger human resources in productive processes. Ageing affects the labour force and its productivity which in turn creates a stumbling block on the growth of the economy.

In present situation it has been observed the aging itself become a problem not only for the society but also for the person belonging to that particular group. It would be pertinent to mention here that all the aged people are not economically dependent, what their basic need is the emotional support from the social structure. The elderly who worked in organized sector are covered by schemes like pensions, gratuities, provided fund etc. the people working in the unorganized sector being not covered by all the above-mentioned scheme are dependent on others and more so on govt. Earlier the problem of the elderly was not serious in India as the numbers were small and the family provided them social security. But at present the demographic changes has been accompanied by some socio-economic changes because of which aged people are suffering a lot of problems.

India is a country with an ancient culture and tradition where elderly enjoys a respectable place in society. Old age and wisdom considered as synonymous in the traditional agrarian Indian culture. Joint family and common land holding were abundant in rural areas. So elder were never a problem. But in the last five decades the fast pace of modernization that has been taking place has seriously affected the status that the elderly enjoyed hitherto. The changing family and kinship bond is a growing concern pertaining to the problems of aging in India. The family and kinship bonds which offered social security for the care of the old have gradually weakened over the past decades under the pressure of industrialization, modernization and value change (Dak 1997). In the traditional Indian agrarian structure elders were respected in the society and old age was not a problem. There were strong social support and observances with regard to the elder care. The elderly not only participated in religious and social activities but their council was highly valued in the familial and community matters. In the traditional Indian agrarian structure elders were respected in the society and old age was not a problem. There were strong social support and observances with regard to the elder care. According to Nyar and Singh due to the rapid transformation in the society, the traditional joint family has been dwindling fast and showing complete signs of disintegration. The growing tendencies towards urbanization and westernization led to the nucleation of the families and promoted individualism and commercialization of the value pattern among younger generation (Jamuna,2000). Increase of dual career families is another striking feature of modern times. Due to work responsibility outside home, women who are traditionally caregivers may not able take care of the elders. Dak argued that with advancing age, most elders lose their family headship role and as a result there is a corresponding decline in their status and power in the family. This process of change is gaining momentum resulting in serious shrinkage of quality care for elderly. Migration of children for better education and occupational opportunities have put them away from their aged parents. This is applicable in the case of the people of both rural and urban areas. Some parents are migrating with their children but it becomes very difficult for them to adjust in the new environment.

III. GENDER AND AGING

There is a gender dimension as well to the issue of aging. Since the life style and role expectation is slightly different in Indian culture, the pattern of aging is likely to show gender difference. According to 1991 census, the distribution of elderly population by marital status indicates significant gender differences. The trend in the 60 plus group shows that 80.7 % of people had their spouse against 44.2 percent female and 15.5 percent of men were widowed against 54% of women. In 1995 20% of male and 50 % of female were widowed among the aged (1997, registrar general of India). In the 70 plus age group 80 percent were widows and 27 % were widower. The reason for the higher widow was the normative practice of young women being married to men much older than them and remarriage being prohibited among women. As a result of longer period of widowhood, many elderly women in India face a double jeopardy i.e. effect of aging and effect of widowhood in a compound manner. At the same time after 40 most of the women suffers from post menopausal difficulties. Although the life expectancy is more in male than that of female, but the healthy life expectancy i.e. disability free is larger in women than man.

IV. HEALTH AND AGING

Health and Human rights have explicit intrinsic connections and has emerged as powerful concepts within the rights-based approach especially so in the backdrop of weakening public health system. A rights-based approach to health uses International

Human Rights treaties and norms to hold governments accountable for their obligations under the treaties. It recognizes the fact that the right to health is a fundamental right of every human being and it implies the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health and that it is one of the fundamental rights of every human being and that governments have a responsibility for the health of their people which can be fulfilled only through the provision of adequate health and social measures. Health problems are supposed to be the major concern of a society as older people are more prone to suffer from ill health than the younger age people. Besides the physical illness, accompanied by multiple disabilities, such as, blindness deafness etc. *In India leading cause of death among the elderly is cardiovascular disease. Under nutrition is also common in this population. Elderly people in low socio economic groups in urban slum or those living alone are at higher risk of poor dietary intake.*

The old aged people are more likely to be victims of poor mental health, which arise from senility, neurosis and extent of self satisfaction. Epidemiological reports that oldest old are affected by some psychogenetic disorder. Depression, suicide and some anxiety disorders are common. The general reasons for suicide among the elderly are depression, destitute conditions and social and economic factors. A world Health Organization study showed study shows that in India the problem of dementia is more among male than female. The health of the elderly people is very much dependent on the living patterns of the elderly people. In India the traditional practice has been for people to live with their children in old age; this is not necessarily with the intention of receiving support; often the rest of the family also benefits from the arrangement. For e.g., when the younger women of the household go to work, the grandparents take care of their children. There exist several living patterns for the elderly such as living with the spouse, living with children, living in old age homes. Living alone or living with a spouse is the most suitable living arrangement for people who are not too old yet, whereas for the oldest-old, living with a child or grandchild is the most stable arrangement. (Welmoth, 1998) Researchers have put in a lot of effort to investigate the determinants are influenced by a variety of factors including number and availability of children and other relatives, kinship patterns of society, locations of household, marital status, physical status, availability of services and physical and mental well being of the elderly (Schafer, 1999; Kan, Park and Change, 2001). The effects of living arrangement on the physical well-being of the elderly have also been examined by researchers. According to them, changes in living arrangements, family structures and mode of retirement affect the old adversely (D'souza 1989). Leaving the parental home for education and employment results in elderly parents having to live alone at home until the children come back (Gaymu, 2003) the overall wellbeing of the elderly consists of their physical and mental and social wellbeing. As the Activity Theory asserts that in order to be happy in old age, individuals need to be active. It argues that if existing roles and relationships are lost it is important to replace them. Replacement to roles and relationships is necessary because when activity –level drops, there is corresponding drop in level of satisfaction. So the traditional practice in India where parents live with their children at old age can be regarded as the best arrangement where grand parents can keep themselves busy as care taker of their grand children.

V. AGING AND WOMEN

Besides the all above mentioned common health problems elderly women are overburdened with some other physical as well as psychological problems. According to NSS 42 nd survey, there were 654 widows and 328 widowers per thousand old persons in rural area. More than 65 % of Indian women live without spouse as comparison to 29 % old men. So, widowhood is a most prevalent stressful event for many elderly women. It often lowers the socio-economic level women. Only 65.46 percent women are literate according to 2011 census and they were unlikely to have had remunerative job in adulthood. Their work as homemaker is never monetized. urban women sometimes get the pension and life insurance money of their deceased spouse which is totally absent in case of rural women. Nor they are likely to hold property exclusively in their hands. These factors increase the dependency of women on others. At the same time women suffers from some additional diseases like anemia, osteoporosis etc. Closely spaced pregnancies, frequent child bearing and period of lactation will set the pattern of specific nutrient deficiencies. The risk of osteoporosis increases after menopause. Low social status, discriminatory practices, early marriage, multiple pregnancies, and poor attention to health are some of the reasons behind poor health of women. Depression is the most common symptom reported to women.

More women than men need to be cared for either in the family or in the institution in the coming year. It is pertinent to mention here that much progress has been made in the the health care facilities in India during last fifty years. But much emphasis has been on the mother and child health with special emphasis on controlling population. Elderly women are largely excluded. In order to improve the health of elderly women, the policies should aim at conserving their physical and social autonomy.

REFERENCES

1. D, Jamuna (2000). Aging in India: Some Key Issues in *Aging International*.
2. Dreze, J and Sen A.K (1991). *Public Action for Social Security Foundation and Strategy* Oxford University press, New Delhi
3. Gamu, J (2003). *The Housing Condition of Elderly People* ,Genus 201-226.
4. R. Schafer (1999): *Determinants of the Living Arrangements of Elderly*. Joint center for Elderly. Joint Center for Housing Studies, Havard University.
5. Rao, Mahadev (2012). *Economic and Financial Aspects of Ageing in India* (A paper presented at International Institute on Ageing, UN, Malta)
6. Wilmoth Janet. M etal (2014) *Gerontology Perspective and Issues*, New York: Springer Publishing Company.